

IoT platform for offshore wind turbine blade structure health monitoring

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Abstract. Wind energy, as renewable energy, is critical in targeting carbon neutrality or net zero emissions in order to address global climate change. Compared with onshore wind turbines, offshore wind turbines enjoy generally higher wind speed, thus producing more electric energy. However, the harsh marine environment, including high winds, wave-induced vibrations and sea and rain corrosion and erosion, can lead to structural damage, reduced operational efficiency and increased maintenance cost. This paper presents a novel Internet of Things (IoT) platform for structural health monitoring (SHM) of the offshore wind turbine's key component, the wind turbine blades. This research focuses on developing a comprehensive, real-time monitoring system that utilises advanced sensor networks, edge computing, and advanced predictive algorithms to strengthen on-time maintenance of turbine blades, while avoiding unnecessary and costly regular maintenance.

1 Introduction

Wind energy is an important contribution to electricity production in both UK and EU as these countries have committed to achieve carbon neutrality. Fig.1 [1] illustrates the estimation of the deployment of wind turbines and their impact on reducing CO₂ from 2008 to 2030. It is clear that wind energy will continue to play a significant role in producing green electricity and reducing emissions.

Wind turbine blades convert energy from the wind's linear motion to rotational motion of the rotor and thereafter to the gear box and the electricity generator, Generally, the turbine blades determine the maximum energy to be gained from the wind and are key elements of large scale offshore wind turbines. In-service turbine blades may experience potential damage from erosion, corrosion, debris and lightning strikes, in addition to normal wear as they age. Failure of turbine blades will limit the function of the whole wind turbine creating a negative impact on energy production.

In relatively recent years the Internet of Things (IoT) has revolutionized numerous industries bringing about unprecedented levels of connectivity and enabling real-time data

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visualization thus increasing operational efficiency [2]. This paper presents a novel IoT platform designed specifically for structural health monitoring (SHM) of offshore wind turbine blades. The research focuses on developing a real-time monitoring system that utilizes advanced sensor networks, edge computing, a cloud database, and advanced predictive algorithms to enhance the maintenance of turbine blades, while improving power production efficiency and reducing maintenance related cost significantly.

Fig. 1. Wind turbine deployment and corresponding CO2 emission reduction [1]

Compared with traditional maintenance strategies for these structures which rely on regularly scheduled inspections and reactive repairs, the use of IoT technology facilitates condition-based maintenance as a more efficient alternative. Instead of performing maintenance activities at predetermined intervals, condition-based maintenance schedules tasks based on the actual condition of the blades, considering the severity, availability of resource and related costs. This not only reduces unnecessary maintenance activities but also ensures that critical issues are responded to promptly, thereby optimizing resource allocation and reducing operational costs.

Additionally the integration of IoT with cloud computing and big data analytics provides a scalable solution for managing the vast amounts of data generated by the sensors. The cloud-based platform can store and process historical sensor data, providing operators with actionable insights and comprehensive reports on the health status of the turbine blades. This centralized system enhances decision-making and allows for remote monitoring, which is particularly advantageous for offshore wind farms located in challenging and inaccessible environments.

2 IoT platform architecture

Fig.2 depicts the overall architecture of the IoT platform for offshore wind turbine blade structure health monitoring. Sensors embedded into the wind turbine blades are connected to the IoT hardware; the sensor data are then processed, packed and transmitted to the cloud data centre through the network and saved in the cloud database. Users access the cloud database to analyse the sensor data to determine the health status of different wind turbines

and blades. Advanced modelling technologies are used for this, such as digital twin and machine learning.

A highlighted feature of the IoT platform is the scalability in relation to the number of installed wind turbines, the database size, and the number of users. The IoT devices connect to the cloud data centre through the network and they are independent to each; adding or removing individual IoT device/sensors won't affect others. As the data or the capacity of the IoT platform increases, the cloud database can be expanded accordingly without reconstructing existing facilities, thus taking advantage of virtualized computing resources, storage resources and network resources. Naturally by using the cloud [3] the user can access the data as long as they have network connectivity with virtually no capacity limit.

Fig. 2. Overview of IoT platform

2.1 Sensor Network

A heterogeneous network of sensors, including QRS sensors, accelerometer and acoustic emission sensors, is utilized to capture a blade health related data as shown in Fig. 3. The QRS sensors, namely hQRS, tQRS, sQRS, are installed in the wind turbine blades, to monitor temperature, moisture and strain respectively at the location of installation. The accelerometer and acoustic emission sensors are used to detect cracking, delamination, debonding and impacts affecting the blade. These sensors are placed along the blade's surface and internally based on structural analysis and optimization algorithms.

2.2 IoT hardware

The DAQ system interfaces with the QRS sensors and AE sensors, and pre-processes the raw sensor data, to reduce network traffic. Pre-determined thresholds will be established to trigger alarms so appropriate action can be taken in time. The DAQ system then sends out the processed data to the microprocessor and it is then transmitted by wireless network to the cloud data centre, as shown in Fig.3. This approach reduces the volume of data transmitted to the central cloud centre, while ensuring timely detection of potential issues and reducing reliance on constant high-bandwidth connectivity.

2.3 Real-time data visualization

The platform features a robust data visualization and alert system, providing stakeholders with real-time dashboards and notifications. This includes a user-friendly interface that displays sensor readings and predictive analytics outcomes. The alert system ensures that critical issues are immediately flagged and addressed, preventing catastrophic failures.

Fig. 3. Sensor network connection to micro-processor

The real-time cloud database stores the relevant sensor data frames in timely order. It enables resilient storage and makes the sensor data available to the users through the internet from different platform such as Windows and Linux computers, as well mobile phones.

The GUI in Fig.4 visualizes the sensor data and gives a brief summary of the blades' status, helping operators and users to quickly understand the wind turbines' current and historic conditions and takes prompt actions if required.

Fig. 4. GUI for real-time sensor database visualization

3 IoT platform testing

The IoT platform is tested to evaluate its functions as designed and to ensure it is suited to service structure health monitoring for offshore wind turbine blades. Both the hardware and software are tested.

3.1 Hardware function testing

Fig.5a is the main hardware unit consisting of the micro-processor, the wireless network adaptor and related accessories, packed in a black box. An Ethernet network is attached to the main unit, which is useful for debugging and testing.

Fig. 5. IoT main hardware unit with micro-processor and wireless network

When the main unit is powered on and Ethernet cable unplugged, the Ethernet port lights are off; when the Ethernet cable is plugged in, the amber light of the Ethernet port is on and the yellow light starts to flash when there is traffic through the Ethernet port; the yellow light will remain on if the traffic stops. The IP address and netmask are obtained, as shown in Fig.5b.

When it is connected to the WIFI network the IP address and DNS are obtained. Figure b shows the IP address of the wireless network is obtained correctly. By pinging to the server of google.com it shows the following information in Fig.5c. The remote IP address of the server (domain name) is correctly resolved, indicating the DNS server is working. The ping results confirm that the wireless network hardware is functioning correctly and is able to connect to the remote servers without packet loss.

The timing device real-time clock is able to keep it synchronized with the network timing server. Fig.6a shows the time and date, which is the same with the time in the laptop when checking.

The hardware platform was tested to run more than 7x24 hours to check the stability. The test ran from 8 August 2023 to 11 October 2023, lasting more than 9x7x24 days.

3.2 Software function testing

The DAQ simulator provides an interface similar the physical DAQ system with a remote database. When accessing the DAQ simulator, the software of IoT platform return the correct date of the DAQ simulator, as shown in Figure.

The real-time cloud database is interfaced wirelessly and can be read and modified by the IoT platform. The IoT platform software is able to read all the sensor data and add more sensor data when new data is available from the DAQ simulator, as shown in Fig.6b.

The main functions of the GUI include display of the sensor data according to the wind turbine number, blade number and sensor number. The selected sensor is verified as shown in Fig.4. When there is an alarm from the DAQ simulator, the corresponding wind turbine will be marked as red in colour, to clearly declare an alarm to the users and operators.

4 Conclusions & future work

This paper reports work aimed at facilitating Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) of the instrumented blade based on the intelligent analysis of data acquired from QRS sensors embedded within the blade. The architecture of the IoT platform has been designed; the hardware and software have been developed and tested to meet the requirements for SHM of offshore wind turbines thus providing a reliable, real-time solution for wind turbine blade SHM. Future work will take advantage of the flexibility of the IoT platform, focus on enhancing its functions, and add more value to the users/stakeholders.

Fig. 6. Evaluation of access to cloud database

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